

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Qodirova Dilnoza Alisher qizi

TOG'AY MUROD ASARLARIDA MILLIY QAHRAMON MASALASI

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX